

THE EFFECT OF RADIATION IN ACUTE DISEASES

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Annotation: In the vast majority of cases, these effects occur with the short-term effect of high doses and high dose rates of radiation. For example, in the atomic explosions in Hiroshima and Nagasaki, the damaging doses of gamma-neutron irradiation of people (several gray) were realized within millionths of a second.

The main distinguishing feature of deterministic effects is their threshold character. In other words, for the occurrence of a particular disease, it is necessary to achieve certain threshold levels of human radiation doses, below which these effects are not clinically manifested.

Keywords: radiation sickness, radiosensitive organs, stochastic effects

The severity of deterministic effects directly depends on the absorbed radiation dose: the higher the dose, the deeper the severity of the lesion. For example, for the skin, the threshold of erythema and dry peeling is approximately 3-5 Gy; cell death in the epidermal and dermal layers, leading to tissue necrosis, occurs after acute irradiation at a dose of about 50 Gy.

With acute, short-term radiation exposure, various forms of acute radiation sickness may occur. Thus, with general irradiation of the entire human body at a dose of about 1 Gy, acute radiation sickness does not occur and deaths are excluded; at doses of 3-5 Gy, as a result of damage to bone marrow stem cells, 50% of those irradiated may die (without treatment) within 60 days. At doses of 5-15 Gy, due to damage to the cell pool of the gastrointestinal tract, the so-called intestinal form of acute radiation sickness occurs, and death is possible after 10-20 days, and at doses over 15 Gy (cerebral form of acute radiation sickness), death occurs in all irradiated patients within 5 days.

Currently, the spectrum of deterministic effects and their dependence on human exposure levels have been sufficiently studied, but there are no final judgments about quantitative differences in exposure thresholds due to individual radiosensitivity of individual representatives of heterogeneous population groups.

As an example, Table 1 shows the threshold doses of some deterministic effects in the most radiosensitive human tissues and organs. The range of threshold doses for different radiosensitive organs and tissues varies. At the same time, it is important to note that the radiation dose thresholds for acute, short-term radiation exposure and for prolonged exposure differ significantly. Consequently, irradiation (in similar total doses), stretched over time, generally increases the threshold level. Undoubtedly, this pattern, determined primarily by the processes of damage repair in the whole organism, is also characteristic of the effects of so-called low doses of radiation (low doses are understood as exposure levels in the ranges of less than 0.2 Gy and dose rate of less than 0.1 Gy/h), especially if we consider that cellular repair systems in the body function more efficiently after irradiation with a low-

power dose than after exposure to a high-power dose. In other words, all other things being equal, acute exposure to ionizing radiation is always more dangerous than chronic, long-term exposure in equivalent doses. Thus, the International Commission on Radiation Protection (ICRP) emphasizes that "... extended (low dose rate) and fractionated exposures are less effective against many biological consequences, including the induction of tumors, than single-dose with a high dose rate."

The next class of effects of radiation exposure is called stochastic (probabilistic, random) effects, which are sometimes called long-term effects of radiation exposure.

Unlike deterministic effects, for which a dose threshold has been proven and exists, and which, as a rule, occur at significant doses of radiation mainly due to the death of most cells in damaged organs or tissues, there is no dose threshold for stochastic consequences, according to modern concepts. This, in turn, means that the implementation of stochastic effects is theoretically possible with an arbitrarily small dose of radiation, while the probability of their occurrence is less, the lower the dose. The question of what this probability is is a key question for an objective understanding of the whole problem.

Scientific Committee on the Effects of Atomic Radiation (NCDAR) The UN and the International Commission on Radiation Protection (ICRP) have concluded that only two main types of stochastic effects of radiation exposure have been proven. The first occurs in somatic cells and may be the cause of cancer in an irradiated

individual. The second type, appearing in the germ tissue of the genital glands, can lead to inherited disorders in the offspring of irradiated people. It is important to emphasize that if the possibility of induction of malignant tumors in irradiated people is a fact proven by world science, so far direct scientific evidence of genetically determined effects of human irradiation has not been obtained. Nevertheless, having direct data on the presence of such effects on other biological objects (plants, cell cultures, microorganisms, small laboratory animals), the ICRP, in order to exclude possible underestimation of their significance, recognized the need to include hereditary effects in the list of stochastic consequences of human exposure. In this context, it is necessary to pay attention to the following fundamental circumstance.

Often, many scientists and doctors who are not familiar enough with modern ideas about the pathogenesis of stochastic effects of radiation, along with malignant tumors and genetic defects, include various somatic diseases in irradiated people who do not have radiation genesis and are path genetically not caused by ionizing radiation in this category of radiation effects. For example, at one time, the so-called premature aging syndrome (premature death) was attributed to this class of effects. Subsequently, after a thorough analysis of scientific information, this syndrome was excluded from the class of stochastic effects of radiation exposure, since it was found that any reduction in life expectancy in irradiated people or experimental animals is associated with excess mortality from radiation-induced cancer.

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